

Studies on combining ability and heterosis in rice

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The usefulness of a particular cross in the exploitation of heterosis in rice is judged by analyzing combining ability. An attempt was made to understand the nature of gene action governing grain yield in heterotic F_1 rice combinations at the Directorate of Rice Research in Hyderabad, India.

For this study, we used 33 genotypes as male parents to make 99 crosses with three cytoplasmic male sterile lines—V20A, IR58025A, and IR62829A—in a line \times tester mating design. The 138 treatments of 99 F_1 s of 3 lines, 33 testers, and 2 traditional varieties—Jaya and Rasi—were laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications in the 1992 dry season (DS). Each treatment (plot) consisted of one row of 15 plants, with one plant hill⁻¹ and 20 \times 15-cm spacing. Five plants from each plot were randomly measured for yield and yield component analysis.

Analysis of variance indicated that differences among treatments, which included 36 parents and 99 hybrids, were highly significant for all characters studied, implying a high degree of genetic differences in the material.

In general, variance due to specific combining ability (SCA) was greater than that due to general combining ability (GCA) for the characters studied, indicating the predominance of nonadditive gene interaction in governing yield and other related traits. This offers the possibility of exploiting heterosis.

Of the 99 F_1 s, 21 cross combinations exhibited >20% yield advantage over the best check Jaya. The table presents the performance, SCA effects of crosses, GCA effects of parents, and standard

Yield performance, SCA effects of crosses, GCA effects of parents, and standard heterosis in heterotic hybrid combinations identified, 1992 dry season.^a

Code	Cross combination	Yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	SCA effect	GCA effect of female	GCA effect of male	Standard heterosis (over Jaya)
A1/R31	IR58025A/Suweon 287 R	27.8	6.63**	1.46**H	4.96**H	75.9**
A3/R15	IR62829A/Chianung Senyu	26.7	5.84**	-0.13 A	6.21**H	68.4**
A3/R26	IR62829A/Mahsuri	25.7	11.17**	-0.13 A	-0.11 A	62.8**
A2/R5	IR58025A/IR46R	24.0	2.71*	1.46**H	5.11**A	51.8**
A2/R17	IR58025A/Suweon 318R	24.0	4.94**	1.46**H	2.88**H	51.8**
A2/R28	IR58025A/ARC11353R	23.0	4.88**	1.46**	1.94 A	45.6**
A1/R30	V20A/UPR254-85-ITCA	22.6	6.75**	-1.33**L	2.41**H	42.4**
A2/R2	IR58025A/IR9761-19-1R	22.4	1.49 ns	1.46**H	4.66**H	41.1**
A3/R4	IR62829A/Vajram R	22.3	2.69*	-0.13 A	4.91**H	40.8**
A3/R9	IR58025A/IR28178-70-2-3R	21.9	2.33 ns	1.46**H	3.36**H	38.7**
A1/R22	V20A/IR2797-125	21.8	3.46**	-1.33**L	4.78**H	37.9**
A2/R32	IR58025A/HKR119	20.9	2.63*	1.46**H	2.15 A	32.3**
A3/R11	IR62829A/IR35366-40-3-3R	20.8	4.67**	-0.13 A	1.54 A	31.6**
A3/R7	IR62829A/IR13419-13-1R	20.5	1.90 ns	-0.13 A	3.96**H	29.8**
A2/R15	IR58025A/Chianung Senyu	20.4	-1.95 ns	1.46**H	6.21**H	29.1**
A2/R14	IR58025A/IET9311	20.3	2.50*	1.46**H	1.61 A	28.6**
A1/R5	V20A/IR46R	19.7	1.17*	-1.33**L	5.11**H	24.7**
A1/R4	V20A/Vajram R	19.6	1.24 ns	-1.33**L	4.94**H	24.2**
A2/R7	IR58025A/IR13419-13-1R	19.6	-0.60 ns	1.46**	3.96**H	23.8**
A1/R18	V20A/IR1361R	19.2	4.78**	-1.33**L	0.96 A	21.5**
A1/R2	V20A/IR9761-19-1R	19.0	0.95 ns	-1.33**L	4.66**H	20.3**

** , * = significant at 1 and 5% level, respectively; ns = not significant, H = high GCA effects, A = average, L = low GCA effects.

heterosis over Jaya. Thirteen of these 21 superior crosses exhibited significant SCA effects. The other eight crosses registered nonsignificant SCA effects. The cross A3/R26 had very high SCA effects but did not rank high in yield. On the other hand, crosses A2/R31 and A3/R15 showed a very high mean yield performance with moderately significant SCA effects. Crosses with nonsignificant SCA effects performed better than some crosses with significant SCA effects (such as A2/R31, A3/R11, A2/R14, A2/R18, etc.).

These results clearly indicated that high-yielding hybrids need not be the ones with high SCA effects and vice versa as reported earlier.

Results showed that of 13 crosses with significant SCA effects, 10 crosses involved one parent with high GCA effects and others had either high, average, or low combining ability effects (see table). This indicates additive as well as nonadditive genetic interactions operating in the crosses studied. ■

Breeding methods — tissue culture

Effects of L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal on plant regeneration in indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Production and maintenance of embryogenic calli and subsequent plant regeneration in higher frequency

are important aspects of tissue culture. A rapid decrease in morphogenetic capacity with age in culture has often been observed. To overcome this problem, several methods have been suggested. We report the promotive effect of L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal on plant regeneration in long-term callus cultures of indica rice.

Callus cultures were raised from 4-d-old coleoptile tissue of indica rice (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Kasturi). Mature

seeds were surface-sterilized and kept for germination on MS0 medium (MS without any growth hormone) for the first 2 d in the dark at $26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and then transferred to 16 h/8 h light/dark. Coleoptile tissues (1 cm long) were dissected from 4-d-old germinating seeds and cultured on MS medium containing 0.5 mg L^{-1} kinetin and 2.5 mg L^{-1} 2,4-D (MS1).

Cultures were initially incubated in the dark at $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 wk and then transferred to a fresh medium and kept under 16 h/8 h light/dark for the next 3 wk. After 6 wk, embryogenic calli were divided into small pieces and transferred to various maintenance media (see table) for 8 mo before they

were transferred to the regeneration medium, MS + 0.5 mg L^{-1} IAA + 4.0 mg L^{-1} BAP.

Callus initiation was observed after 4 d of inoculation. Compact and globular embryogenic calli were clearly visible after 20 d of culture initiation (Fig. 1). The first 45 embryogenic calli clumps were transferred on various maintenance media where they were subcultured at 4-wk intervals for 8 mo. During maintenance, somatic embryoid-like structures (Fig. 2) were observed on a maintenance medium (MS1) containing 100 mg L^{-1} L-tryptophan.

After 8 mo, calli maintained on medium containing L-tryptophan, L-

proline, and activated charcoal remained embryogenic. Nearly half of the calli clumps (24 of 45 embryogenic calli clumps) maintained without L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal turned blackish and lost their embryogenic potential. When the remaining embryogenic calli clumps (approximate wt 0.29 g) were transferred to the regeneration medium (MS + 0.5 mg L^{-1} IAA + 4.0 mg L^{-1} BAP), a few calli clumps (23.8%) showed green shoot bud induction after 14 d. Among calli clumps obtained from a medium containing L-tryptophan and activated charcoal, 71.4% showed green shoot bud after 8 d of transfer on a regeneration medium. These shoot buds further proliferated into multiple shoots (Fig. 3).

The maximum average number of plantlets (5.3 per calli clump) was recovered from calli clumps maintained on a medium containing 100 mg L^{-1} L-tryptophan and 1% activated charcoal. A maintenance medium containing L-proline (100 mg L^{-1}) and activated charcoal (1%) was suitable for regenerating green plantlets. Regenerated plantlets were counted after 6 wk of subculture. Calli clumps maintained without L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal produced only 1.3 plantlets per calli clump. The regenerated plantlets were rooted on MS medium

Effects of L-tryptophan, L-proline, and activated charcoal (added to MS medium) on plant regeneration from long-term callus cultures of indica rice.

Maintenance medium (mg L^{-1}) + (supplements) ^a	Calli forming shoot buds (no.)	Calli forming shoots (%)	Green plantlets (no.)
MS1	5	23.8	7
MS1 + L-tryptophan (100)	9	42.8	33
MS1 + L-tryptophan (100) + activated charcoal (1%)	15	71.4	80
MS1 + L-proline (100)	8	39.0	35
MS1 + L-proline (100) + activated charcoal (1%)	14	66.7	65

^aMaintenance media (MS1) = MS + 0.5 mg L^{-1} 2,4-D + 0.5 mg L^{-1} kinetin. Regeneration media = MS + 0.5 mg L^{-1} IAA + 4.0 mg L^{-1} BAP. Data are average of three replications treatment⁻¹; each treatment consists of seven calli (average weight 0.29 g replicate⁻¹). In each case, 21 calli were plated. The experiment was repeated two times.

1. Nodular and embryogenic calli after 20 d of culture initiation.

2. Initiation of somatic embryoid-like structures from embryogenic callus on MS1, a maintenance medium containing 0.5 mg L^{-1} 2,4-D + 0.5 mg L^{-1} kinetin + 100 mg L^{-1} L-tryptophan.

3. Multiple shoot proliferation on MS medium containing 0.5 mg L^{-1} IAA + 4.0 mg L^{-1} BAP (after 28 d of transfer).

4. Regenerated plantlets showing rooting on MS medium containing 1.0 mg IBA L⁻¹.

containing 1.0 mg IBA L⁻¹ (Fig. 4) and were transferred to pots.

Results indicated the usefulness of L-tryptophan and activated charcoal in increasing regeneration of green plants from long-term callus cultures of indica rice. ■

Grain quality

Modeling water uptake and degree of polish of milled rice

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This study was undertaken to model the process of water uptake behavior during cooking and to correlate water uptake with degree of polish for two varieties (coarse Jaya and scented fine Basmati) commonly grown in the western part of Uttar Pradesh, India. Rough rice samples were collected from a farmer's field just after harvest, cleaned, and shade-dried up to milling moisture content (14% dry basis). These were then shelled and polished in a

Satake rice sheller and polisher. Milling / polish time varied from 0 s to 60 s to control the degree of bran removal (degree of polish) with an increment of 15 s. The degree of polish of milled samples ranged from 2.7% to 8.4% for Jaya and 2.9% to 8.5% for Basmati at 15 s and 60 s, respectively.

The 1,000-kernel weight of Jaya (28.6 g) was higher than that of Basmati (24.5 g). The length and width-thickness ratio of Jaya were 8.67 mm and 3.04 mm, respectively, and those of Basmati were 11.09 mm and 5.13 mm. The angle of repose of Basmati (32°) was wider than Jaya's (24.8°). Bulk and true density were determined by measuring the weight of known volumes of samples and by the method of relative density, respectively. Porosity, the index of void space in the bulk, was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Porosity} = \frac{(\text{True density} - \text{bulk density})}{\text{True density}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Table 1 shows the bulk density, true density, and porosity of the two rice varieties.

Table 1. Physical and gravimetric properties of Jaya and Basmati rice.

Property	Jaya	Basmati
Size (mm)		
Length	8.7	11.1
Width	2.8	2.0
Thickness	2.0	1.8
1,000-kernel weight (g)	28.6	24.5
Bulk density (g cc ⁻¹)	0.6	0.5
True density (g cc ⁻¹)	1.3	1.0
Porosity (%)	51.2	51.4
Angle of repose(°)	24.8	32.6

Table 2. Degree of polish, head yield, and water uptake of Jaya and Basmati rice varieties.

Time of milling (s)	Jaya			Basmati		
	D _p ^a	H _y	W _{up}	D _p	H _y	W _{up}
0	0	89.0	-	0	85.0	-
15	2.7	64.3	355	2.9	65.1	352
30	4.6	61.9	357	4.9	63.9	362
45	6.7	58.1	362	6.4	63.1	371
60	8.4	57.2	368	8.5	63.0	384

^aD_p = degree of polish (% on brown rice basis), H_y = head yield (%), and W_{up} = water uptake (g).

Water uptake and kernel elongation after cooking were also determined (Table 2). Kernel elongation was 35% more in Basmati than in Jaya for 6% degree of polish. A similar observation was recorded for different samples of milled rice. Water uptake was found to be more for the same degree of polish for Basmati than for Jaya. Water uptake behavior for Jaya and Basmati can be described by the following equation:

$$W_{up} = A \times e^{B D_p} \quad (2)$$

where A = 1.71 and B = 0.91.

This mathematical expression describes the kinetics of water uptake (mL) and its relation with degree of polish (%) satisfactorily under obtainable conditions. The correlation coefficient and standard error of estimate for the above equation were 0.987 and 0.089, respectively. ■

Breeding of Gan wan nuo 5, a new high-quality glutinous indica variety

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Gan wan nuo 5, released in 1993 by the Jiangxi Provincial Seed Board, is a new glutinous indica rice variety with high quality. It was derived from the cross MY82166/Ma ba xian nuo. MY82166 is an indica rice with high resistance to blast, whereas Ma ba xian nuo is an aromatic glutinous indica variety. Gan wan nuo 5 is suitable for later season planting in the double-cropped area of southern China and single-cropped area of central China. Yield of this variety averaged 6.8 t ha⁻¹ in double-cropped areas; it was 7.5 t ha⁻¹ in single-cropped areas. This yield was 7% more than that of Jing Nuo 6, a glutinous check, and nearly the same as that of Shan you 63, a check hybrid. Because of its high quality and other good traits (see table), the award-winning Gan wan nuo 5 is replacing Jing Nuo 6 in many areas.